

Factors associated with use of herbs and dietary supplements in women with uterine fibroids

Mila Kirkova^{1,2}, Emilia Naseva³, Vidin Kirkov³

¹ Medical Faculty, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

² University Obstetrics and Gynecology Hospital "Mother's Home", Sofia, Bulgaria

³ Faculty of Public Health "Prof. Tzecomir Vodenitcharov, MD, DSc", Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Vidin Kirkov (vkirkov@fz.mu-sofia.bg)

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Abstract

Uterine fibroids are among the most common benign gynecological diseases and are characterized by diverse clinical symptoms and a significant impact on quality of life. In recent years, there has been growing interest in the use of herbs and nutritional supplements as a complementary therapeutic approach for this disease.

The aim of the present study was to analyze the use of herbs and nutritional supplements among women with uterine fibroids and to assess its relationship with the clinical characteristics of the disease.

The study included 65 women hospitalized at the Second Gynecological Clinic of the University Obstetrics and Gynecology Hospital "Mother's Home" in 2024 with a diagnosis of uterine fibroids and indications for surgical treatment. A survey method comprising a questionnaire and a face-to-face interview was applied. The data were subjected to descriptive and analytical statistical analyses.

The results showed that 61.5% of the patients used dietary supplements, with vitamins and minerals being the predominant supplements. The use of herbs was more limited but included plants with potential hemostatic and anti-inflammatory effects. Anemia was identified in 44.6% of the participants, some of whom used iron-containing medications, including combined products containing herbal components. A statistically significant relationship was found between heavy menstrual bleeding and the use of nutritional supplements.

The use of herbs and nutritional supplements was widespread among women with uterine fibroids and correlated with the severity of clinical symptoms. More active clinical oversight of their rational use is needed.

Keywords

anemia, dietary supplements, phytotherapy, uterine fibroids

Introduction

Uterine fibroids are among the most common benign gynecological diseases in women of reproductive age. Their incidence increases with age, and they affect a significant proportion of the female population, often causing significant clinical symptoms (Bulun 2013).

The clinical presentation is diverse and includes heavy and prolonged menstruation, pelvic pain, anemia, and symptoms associated with compression of adjacent organs. These manifestations often lead to a significant deterioration in quality of life and may prompt patients to seek medical care and undergo surgical treatment.

In recent years, there has been increased interest in the use of herbs and nutritional supplements as part of complementary approaches to the treatment of various chronic noncommunicable diseases. This behavior is explained by patients' preference for more natural treatment methods and their desire to manage symptoms outside the framework of conventional therapy (Ekor 2014).

The use of such products among women with uterine fibroids is often intended to influence hormonal balance, reduce bleeding, or alleviate pain symptoms. However, the available scientific data on their effectiveness and safety remain limited, and these products are often taken without medical supervision (Izzo and Ernst 2009).

The factors determining the use of herbs and dietary supplements in this group of patients also remain insufficiently understood. Analysis of these factors is essential for a better understanding of health behavior and for optimizing physicians' approaches to consultation and follow-up.

Appropriate statistical analysis and interpretation of the obtained data are key elements of this type of research and require the precise organization of data and the use of appropriate analytical methods (Vaseva and Naseva 2014; Naseva 2021).

In this context, the present study aimed to investigate the use of herbs and dietary supplements among women with uterine fibroids and the factors associated with this behavior.

Objective

The aim of this study was to analyze the frequency and patterns of herbal and dietary supplement use among women with uterine fibroids and to identify factors associated with their use.

Materials and methods

The study subjects were women diagnosed with uterine fibroids and hospitalized at the Second Gynecological Clinic of the University Obstetrics and Gynecology Hospital "Mother's Home."

The study was conducted in 2024 and included 65 patients admitted for surgical treatment. All participants were diagnosed with uterine fibroids, as confirmed by clinical and imaging methods.

The study was conducted using a survey method that included the completion of a questionnaire by the patients and a face-to-face interview to clarify the information collected.

The survey contained questions concerning demographic characteristics, clinical manifestations of the disease, menstrual and reproductive status, and the use of medications, herbs, and nutritional supplements.

The results were analyzed statistically using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 29. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and proportions, and quantitative variables were presented as medians and interquartile ranges (IQRs; 25th–75th percentiles).

Binary logistic regression analysis was applied to assess the factors associated with the use of herbs and dietary supplements, and the results were presented as odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs). *P*-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Statistical analysis was performed according to established principles for working with biomedical information (Naseva 2021, 2024a, 2024b). The results are presented in tables and graphs (Vaseva and Naseva 2014).

Results

The study included 65 women with uterine fibroids who were hospitalized at the Second Gynecological Clinic of the University Obstetrics and Gynecology Hospital "Mother's Home" for surgical treatment in 2024. The study group had a heterogeneous age structure, with a median age of 45 years (IQR: 40–49) and an age range of 30–82 years. The age group with the highest relative proportion was 36–45 years, which corresponds to the active reproductive period (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Distribution by age group.

Regarding sociodemographic characteristics, almost half of the patients were residents of the capital (47.7%), whereas the remainder were distributed among smaller towns (30.8%), district centers (10.8%), and villages (10.8%). Uterine fibroids were diagnosed almost exclusively by ultrasonography (95.4%), confirming the leading role of this method in the diagnostic process (Table 1).

Regarding menstrual status, 13.8% of the women were postmenopausal, whereas the remainder had a high frequency of pathological changes. A total of 80.4% reported menstrual cycle disorders, the most common of which were heavy menstruation (67.9%), painful menstruation (60.7%), and the presence of blood clots (58.9%) (Table 2).

The clinical presentation was dominated by abdominal distension (72.3%) and pain (55.4%), with a significant

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics and method of diagnosis of the patients ($n = 65$).

		<i>n</i>	%
Residence	Sofia (capital)	31	47.7
	District center	7	10.8
	Smaller town	20	30.8
	Village	7	10.8
Method used to diagnose uterine fibroids	Ultrasound examination by ObGyn	62	95.4
	Other method	3	4.6

Table 2. Characteristics of menstrual status and menstrual cycle disorders.

		<i>n</i>	%
Menopause	No	56	86.2
	Yes	9	13.8
Menstrual cycle characteristics in terms of regularity	Regular	54	83.1
	Irregular	2	3.1
	Menopause	9	13.8
Menstruation	Normal	11	19.6
	Heavy, painful, or presence of coagulums	45	80.4
Heavy menstruation	No	18	32.1
	Yes	38	67.9
Painful menstruation	No	22	39.3
	Yes	34	60.7
Menstruation with coagulums	No	23	41.1
	Yes	33	58.9

proportion of patients also reporting urinary (47.7%) and defecatory disorders (46.2%). Dyspareunia was reported by 32.3% of the patients. The proportion of women with anemia (44.6%) was particularly notable, with 9.2% requiring blood transfusions, emphasizing the severity of blood loss (Table 3).

Regarding reproductive status, 72.3% of the patients had given birth, indicating a predominance of parous women in the study group. At the same time, more than one-third (36.9%) reported a history of abortion. This result reflects the complex interaction between uterine fibroids and reproductive function, as a history of abortion may be associated with both reproductive problems and increased medical intervention in this population. Nulliparous women represented a smaller proportion, although their presence emphasizes that uterine fibroids affect women regardless of whether they have previously given birth. Hormonal therapy was administered to 36.9% of the patients.

The use of nutritional supplements and alternative remedies was widespread, with 61.5% of the women reporting the use of such products (Fig. 2). The use of herbs remained relatively limited (9.2%) but was characterized by a wide variety of products. The plants used included well-known species such as calendula, nettle, St. John's wort, and red clover, as well as herbs specific to gynecological practice, such as yarrow, Turta herb (African marigold), shepherd's purse (*Capsella bursa-pastoris*), and cat's whiskers (*Orthosiphon aristatus*). This range suggests a

Table 3. Frequency of the main clinical manifestations among patients with uterine fibroids.

		<i>n</i>	%
Anemia	No	36	55.4
	Yes	29	44.6
Performed blood transfusion	No	59	90.8
	Yes	6	9.2
Disorders in urination	No	34	52.3
	Yes	31	47.7
Constipation	No	35	53.8
	Yes	30	46.2
Abdominal distension	No	18	27.7
	Yes	47	72.3
Pain syndrome	No	29	44.6
	Yes	36	55.4
Dyspareunia	No	44	67.7
	Yes	21	32.3

Figure 2. Use of dietary supplements among participants.

focus on influencing blood flow, inflammatory processes, and hormonal balance. The use of vitamins was more common (33.8%), particularly vitamins C and D. The intake of preparations containing iron or vitamin B12 was reported by 12.3% of the patients and was consistent with the frequency of anemia. This group also included combination products known as "herbal blood," which combine iron salts with plant extracts. These preparations represent an intermediate approach between conventional drug therapy and phytotherapy and are probably preferred because of their perceived better tolerability and more natural composition.

The intake of minerals (12.3%), most commonly magnesium, and other plant-based supplements, including turmeric, spirulina, and aloe vera, complemented the profile of the products used and reflected the desire for a comprehensive approach to symptom management (Table 4).

Table 4. Use of herbs, nutritional supplements, and micronutrients among the study participants.

		<i>n</i>	%
Use nutritional supplements	No	25	38.5
	Yes	40	61.5
Use herbs	No	59	90.8
	Yes	6	9.2
Use preparations containing iron or vitamin B12	No	57	87.7
	Yes	8	12.3
Use vitamins C, D	No	43	66.2
	Yes	22	33.8
Use minerals	No	57	87.7
	Yes	8	12.3
Use other nutritional supplements	No	59	90.8
	Yes	6	9.2

Analysis of the factors associated with supplement use showed that heavy menstrual bleeding, no history of abortion, and hormonal therapy were statistically significant predictors of this behavior (Table 5). The results showed that heavy menstrual bleeding increased the odds of supplement use ninefold, whereas previous or current hormonal therapy increased the odds 11-fold. A history of abortion was a protective factor, and women without a history of abortion were 5.5 times more likely to use supplements.

Table 5. Factors associated with the use of dietary supplements: results of the logistic regression analysis.

Factors	OR	95% CI	P
Heavy menstruation	9.26	1.78–48.30	0.008
History of abortion	0.18	0.04–0.95	0.043
Undergoing or underwent hormone therapy	11.22	2.09–60.05	0.005

Discussion

The present study examined the behavior of patients with uterine fibroids regarding the use of herbs and dietary supplements, and the results showed a high frequency of complementary remedy use. These data can be interpreted in the context of growing interest in integrating different therapeutic approaches in chronic gynecological diseases (Stewart et al. 2017).

The high frequency of menstrual disorders, including heavy and painful menstruation, is consistent with the characteristic clinical presentation of uterine fibroids (Munro et al. 2011). The significant proportion of patients with anemia reflects the clinical severity of chronic blood loss and the need for adequate therapeutic management. In this context, the relatively limited use of iron-containing preparations, including combined products with herbal components, indicates a possible mismatch between the severity of the condition and the choice of therapy.

The high frequency of dietary supplement use in the study group is comparable to data from other studies showing the widespread use of these products among patients with chronic diseases (Frass et al. 2012). The more

frequent use of vitamins and minerals than of herbal products probably reflects greater trust in products with standardized compositions and clearly defined doses.

At the same time, despite their less frequent use, the medicinal plants demonstrated considerable diversity and were intended to influence the main symptoms of the disease. The use of plants such as yarrow, Turta herb, shepherd's purse, and cat's whiskers suggests a search for agents with hemostatic effects, which is consistent with the predominant complaint of heavy menstruation. In addition, plants such as nettle and calendula are associated with potential anti-inflammatory and tonic effects, which probably determine their use in this population (Wuttke et al. 2003).

Of particular interest is the fact that the herbs used included both widely known phytotherapeutic agents and those characteristic of traditional folk medicine. This observation can be interpreted as an indication that modern and traditional approaches are combined in the independent management of symptoms.

The use of nutritional supplements containing vitamins and minerals also corresponded to the clinical symptoms. The intake of vitamins C and D may be associated with general strengthening and immunomodulatory effects, whereas the use of magnesium is probably intended to alleviate pain and muscle discomfort.

Preparations containing iron and vitamin B12 occupy a significant place because they are used in relation to the high prevalence of anemia. This group also includes combined products containing iron and plant extracts. These products occupy an intermediate position between pharmacological treatment and phytotherapy and are probably preferred because of their perceived better tolerability and lower risk of adverse effects.

The observed relationship between the severity of menstrual symptoms and the use of nutritional supplements confirms that the intensity of clinical manifestations is a major factor determining patient behavior. The more frequent use of supplements among women undergoing hormonal therapy can be viewed as an indication of greater commitment to the treatment process and a desire to combine different therapeutic approaches.

The differences related to reproductive status, including the lower frequency of supplement use among women with a history of abortion, indicate the possible influence of individual behavioral characteristics and health attitudes on therapeutic choices.

The results emphasize the need for more active communication between physicians and patients regarding the use of herbs and dietary supplements. Insufficient discussion of these agents may lead to uncoordinated use and potential drug interactions (Izzo and Ernst 2009).

The limitations of the present study are related to the small sample size and single-center design, which limit the generalizability of the results. In addition, the survey method used introduces the possibility of subjective bias. Nevertheless, the results provide valuable information about patient behavior and identify directions for future research (Naseva 2021).

Inferences and conclusion

The present study showed that uterine fibroids were characterized by pronounced clinical symptoms, dominated by menstrual disorders and anemia, which significantly affected the patients' quality of life. The results confirmed that the disease was associated with complex medical and behavioral aspects, including an active search for complementary therapeutic agents.

A high frequency of nutritional supplement use was identified, with vitamins and minerals being the most commonly used products. Despite their lower frequency of use, the herbs were diverse and were intended to influence the main clinical manifestations, particularly heavy menstruation. The use of plants with presumed hemostatic and anti-inflammatory effects indicates purposeful behavior among patients.

A significant finding was the relationship between the severity of clinical symptoms and the use of nutritional

supplements, indicating that patients more frequently resorted to complementary remedies when experiencing more pronounced symptoms. At the same time, the relatively limited use of iron-containing pharmaceutical preparations, including combined products with herbal components, among patients with anemia raises questions regarding optimal therapeutic management.

The data emphasize the need for a more active role of medical specialists in discussing and monitoring the use of herbs and nutritional supplements. A lack of sufficient information and coordination may lead to irrational use and potential risks to patients.

In conclusion, the use of herbs and nutritional supplements among women with uterine fibroids was widespread and closely associated with clinical symptoms. This finding indicates the need for an integrated approach in medical practice, including actively informing, monitoring, and guiding patients toward the safe and rational use of complementary therapeutic methods.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

M. Kirkova <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9725-8901>

E. Naseva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1282-8441>

V. Kirkov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8596-5677>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.